

Determination of Parachor in Solution. Part I.

BY SUSIL KUMAR RAY.

The determination of parachor at the present time has helped to solve many intricate and difficult problems of structural chemistry. The main drawback of the method is its limitations in the case of the liquid or fused state of matter only. There are substances of very high melting points, as well as compounds which decompose on fusion, the determination of parachors of which is either difficult or impossible. To get over this difficulty the present investigation was undertaken to find out the applicability of the straight line mixture law in the determination of parachor of solids dissolved in liquids. An attempt was made by Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) to determine parachor of substances in solution. They considered a few simple binary liquid mixtures, and had shown that in solution parachor obeys the simple mixture law. No systematic investigations appear to have been made in this direction except a few isolated cases. In the present paper the surface tension and the density of the pure solvent as well as those of the solutions were determined and from a knowledge of the parachor of the former that of the solute was calculated, on the assumption that parachors obey the straight line mixture law.

The surface tension was determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure; the apparatus employed being of the usual Sugden type. The determination of parachors in solutions, particularly in dilute solutions, requires that all experimental data should be as accurate as possible. All the substances used were, therefore, very carefully purified by distillation or repeated crystallisation. Pressure differences were read correct to 0.03 mm. and the error is probably not more than 0.01 mm. Three bubblers were employed for every observation and five readings were taken with each. The surface tension was calculated from the mean of these fifteen readings. The bubblers were restandardised before each mixture was investigated. Densities were determined by means of a 10 c.c. specific gravity bottle.

The parachor of the solute was calculated from the following relations, as in the work of Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*).

$$P_m = M_m \cdot r^{\frac{1}{2}} / D$$

$$P_m = P(1-x)P_x \cdot x$$

$$M_m = M_s(1-x)M_x \cdot x$$

where r and D are the surface tension and density of the solution, P_m , P and P_x are the parachors of the solution, solvent and the solute respectively, while M_m , M_s and M_x are the respective molecular weights and x is the molecular fraction of the solute.

In the present paper data are given for seventeen different solutions. The solutes examined were simple organic ring-compounds in order to find out the effect of ring structure on the parachor contribution as well (*cf.* Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 499). The solvents employed were both associated and non-associated, of every possible type with widely different chemical nature, so that any effects due to surface adsorption might be detected.

It will be seen from the following tables that the determination of parachor of the solute in solution agrees very closely, with a few exception, with the values either calculated or determined in the fused state. The agreement is most complete generally in very dilute solution and is dependent on the concentration of the solution. In this connection it is to be noted that in liquid mixtures the values are generally independent of the concentration of the solution as is evident from the work of Hammick and Andrew (*loc. cit.*). It is also of much interest to note that in the present series, the surface tension is increased by the dissolution of a solid in the liquid. In liquid mixtures the contrary is generally found to be the case (*cf.* Hammick and Andrew, *loc. cit.*).

It will be found that abnormal results were obtained in three cases, *viz.*, naphthalene in chloroform and phenanthrene in acetone and in carbon tetrachloride. In the case of phenanthrene in acetone the value is found to be lower by about 60 units, while in the other two cases the values are higher by about 20 and 50 units. It is presumed that in these cases either association between the solute molecules or between the solute and the solvent molecules or some kind of dissociation is taking place. The small variations found in some cases are due probably to Gibb's surface adsorption effect.

In the following table, the parachor of the substances determined in the fused state, where possible, are given, so that the values determined in solution may be compared. The density was determined by means of a U-shaped pycnometer as employed by Sugden

Parachor in the Fused State.

TABLE I.

	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
Naphthalene	80.8°	0.9751	32.03	312.3 (312.5 B&S)	313.0
α -Naphthol	98.0	1.1130	40.02	329.4 (336.7 B&S)	333.0
Coumarin	99.8	1.1780	41.81	315.2	314.0
8-Oxyquinoline	98.5	1.1271	39.68	322.8	323.6
Phenanthrene	120.0	1.0370	36.34	420.4	418.0

Parachors of naphthalene and α -naphthol in the fused state have been determined by Bhatnagar and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 263).

Parachor in Solution.

In the following tables x is the molar fraction of solute, M_m the mean molecular weight of the solution, P_m the mean parachor and P_x , the parachor of the solute. Except a few cases the determinations of surface tension and the density were carried out between the temperature of 30-32°.

TABLE II.

Naphthalene in benzene.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
0.0	0.8681	27.38	78	205.5	...	
0.03101	0.8802	28.54	79.55	208.9	312.6	
0.04650	0.8847	28.89	80.32	210.5	311.1	
0.08569	0.8900	29.12	82.27	214.7	312.7	
0.09592	0.8946	29.46	82.79	215.6	310.7	
					mean 311.8	313.0

TABLE III.
Naphthalene in carbon tetrachloride.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	1.5920	26.55	153.83	219.3	...	
0.03746	1.5576	26.65	152.80	222.7	312.3	
0.05480	1.5429	26.66	152.52	224.6	312.6	
0.08872	1.5232	27.10	151.57	227.3	311.1	
0.1089	1.5094	27.51	151.04	229.2	310.2	
				mean	311.6	313.0

TABLE IV.
Naphthalene in chloroform.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	1.4701	26.37	119.37	184.1	...	
0.03461	1.4472	27.46	119.73	189.4	338.1	
0.06218	1.4185	27.35	119.95	193.4	333.4	
0.07137	1.4179	28.02	120.08	194.9	334.7	
				mean	335.4	313.0

TABLE V.
 α -Naphthol in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	0.9718	35.52	79	198.5	...	
0.02983	0.9814	36.40	80.95	202.6	335.4	
0.03927	0.9857	35.71	81.57	203.7	333.6	
0.04932	0.9876	36.99	82.21	205.3	334.6	
				mean	334.5	333.0

TABLE VI.
 α -Naphthol in ethyl acetate.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	0.8885	22.66	88	216.1	...	
0.02453	0.8964	23.22	89.38	218.9	331.7	
0.03639	0.9014	23.71	90.04	220.4	332.6	
0.07962	0.9185	24.51	92.47	224.1	316.5	
0.1237	0.9350	25.17	94.91	227.4	308.1	333.0

TABLE VII.

Coumarin in benzene.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
0.04542	0.8881	28.24	81.09	210.5	314.8	
0.05772	0.8950	28.57	81.93	211.6	311.9	
0.1234	0.9278	29.45	86.39	216.9	297.4	314.0

TABLE VIII.

Coumarin in chloroform.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
0.05693	1.4404	26.99	120.91	191.4	312.6	
0.08420	1.4316	27.84	121.64	195.0	313.5	
0.1111	1.4253	28.69	122.32	198.6	315.1	314.3

mean 313.7

TABLE IX.

Coumarin in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
0.02320	0.9851	36.61	80.58	201.2	313.6	
0.06197	0.9952	37.02	83.14	205.8	316.3	
0.09931	1.0092	38.03	85.65	210.9	323.4	314.0

TABLE X.

8-Oxyquinoline in benzene.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{\text{calc.}}$
0.01810	0.8805	28.31	79.23	207.6	320.3	
0.02238	0.8838	28.61	79.50	208.1	321.8	
0.03215	0.8886	28.81	80.16	209.0	323.4	
0.04889	0.8952	29.26	81.28	211.2	322.8	

mean 322.08

323.6

TABLE XI.

8-Oxyquinoline in carbon tetrachloride.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.01748	1.5674	25.98	153.65	221.0	321.1	
0.02483	1.5637	26.00	153.60	221.8	322.2	
0.05498	1.5577	26.82	153.28	224.0	305.7	
0.09877	1.5295	27.20	153.02	228.4	311.9	323.6

TABLE XII.

Xanthone in chloroform.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.01799	1.4526	26.42	120.73	188.3	421.8	
0.03049	1.4513	27.01	121.68	191.2	419.8	
				mean 420.8		419.9

TABLE XIII.

Xanthone in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.01663	0.9803	36.11	80.95	202.3	420.7	
0.02749	0.9867	36.46	82.22	204.7	421.9	
				mean 421.3		419.9

TABLE XIV.

Phenanthrene in benzene.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.03308	0.8813	28.15	81.31	212.5	417.3	
0.05852	0.8926	28.95	83.85	217.9	417.0	
				mean 417.2		418.0

TABLE XV.

Phenanthrene in carbon tetrachloride.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.02452	1.5555	26.44	154.46	225.3	464.9	
0.03297	1.5503	26.90	154.59	227.2	469.2	
				mean 467.1		418.0

TABLE XVI.

Phenanthrene in acetone.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	0.7830	23.29	58	162.8	...	
0.02764	0.8065	23.84	61.32	168.0	351.0	
0.05230	0.8252	24.54	64.21	173.2	361.4	

TABLE XVII.

Anthracene in nitrobenzene.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	1.1928	43.06	123	264.1	—	
0.01091	1.1904	42.96	123.54	265.8	419.1	
0.01177	1.1893	42.83	123.59	265.9	416.5	
				mean 417.8		418.0

TABLE XVIII.

Dithiol thiodiazol in alcohol.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .	$P_{calc.}$
0.0	0.7853	21.42	46	126.0	...	
0.01401	0.8038	22.22	47.46	128.0	264.2	
0.02752	0.8236	23.01	48.84	129.9	265.3	
				mean 264.8		267.7

It will be observed that the parachor values for α -naphthol in dilute pyridine and ethyl acetate solutions agree well with the calculated value 333; whereas in the fused state the substance gives a much lower value of 329.4. This is evidently due to some incipient decomposition or oxidation at the melting point. The red colour of the fused substance seems to support this idea.

It will be evident from the preceding tables that by the solution of a solid in a liquid the parachor of the mixture is increased and the increment of the parachor is proportional to the concentration of

the solution. This relation is somewhat similar to that observed by Raoult in the diminution of vapour pressure of the solvent by the dissolution of solids, and is best shown by the following curves obtained by plotting P_m against x . This is what can be expected considering the additive character of the parachor function.

FIG. 1.

A in CCl_4 , B in C_6H_6 , C in C_5H_5N & D in $CHCl_3$.

SUMMARY.

1. Parachor of simple ring compounds were determined in solution and it was found that parachor obeys the straight line mixture law in dilute solutions.

2. The values obtained in the solution are found to be dependent on the concentration of the solution.

3. By the dissolution of a solid in a liquid the resulting parachor of the mixture is increased over that of the solvent and the increment is proportional to the concentration.

4. The determinations of inorganic compounds in solution are under investigation.

My grateful thanks are due to Prof P. R. Rây of the University College of Science and to Prof A. Maitra for the kind interest they took in the work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received May 24, 1934.

